

RADIOBLOCKS

Project ID: 101093934

Dissemination Plan

Deliverable:	D1.2
Lead beneficiary:	JIVE
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1. Executive Summary

An important part of the RADIOBLOCKS strategy is to ensure the dissemination of project results and products to as wide a range of research fields and industry sectors as possible. It is thus crucial to ensure the early identification of both high-impact RADIOBLOCKS technologies and the appropriate (industrial) target sectors. This document describes the ambition, boundaries, means, resources, and risks, to develop a dissemination strategy. Actions to ensure the long-term and sustainable exploitation of the project beyond its formal contract duration will be identified and executed.

Since this is the first step into such an unexplored area, the plan starts with brainstorming sessions to survey the knowledge within the current collaboration. Such brainstorming will be the basis for further exploration using targeted questionnaires for the whole collaboration. The results of the questionnaires will be used to establish successive steps.

Since most delivered products are expected by the end of the project, this plan will be evolving throughout RADIOBLOCKS as more details and options are explored and identified. This document reflects the vision of the dissemination at the beginning of the project. This approach, however, requires a frequent scanning of the results and matching them with our ambition and intermediate goals. This process will be coordinated by WP1 and, in particular, by JIVE's communication officer.

2. Objectives and Goals

The primary objective of this dissemination plan is to create effective communication channels to share results, findings, and outcomes of RADIOBLOCKS with relevant stakeholders and a broader audience. Through strategic communication, the plan aims to maximize RADIOBLOCKS's impact by fostering understanding, engagement, and exploitation of the project's results.

In the Grant Agreement (Part A, Section 2.2), the measures to maximize the impact of the project through dissemination, exploitation and communication are summarized. The expected project's outcomes are identified:

- Scientific discoveries
- Technical developments
- Software and simulated data products
- Technical design plans
- Radiofrequency interference mitigation
- Industrial collaborations
- General public interest

This plan updates and formalizes the actions and the dissemination channels described in the Grant Agreement by providing a communication and dissemination strategy and the tools to implement it.

2.1. Goals

Goal		Metrics
Raise Awareness	Increase awareness among the identified target audiences about the project's objectives, activities, and achievements.	Measure website visits, social media reach, and media coverage related to RADIOBLOCKS.
Share Knowledge and Findings	Disseminate project findings, research outcomes, and insights to the scientific community, practitioners, policymakers, and the public.	Track downloads, citations, and mentions in research publications and media.
Facilitate Knowledge Transfer	Enable the transfer of practical knowledge and actionable insights to relevant stakeholders, encouraging the application of the project's outcomes in real-world scenarios.	Monitor the adoption of project outcomes in radio astronomy, relevant industries and practical applications.
Engage Stakeholders	Foster engagement and dialogue among stakeholders, including project partners, collaborators, experts, prospect industrial partners, and other identified audiences.	Measure participation rates in workshops, webinars, and online discussions.

Empower End-Users	Empower radio astronomers with the knowledge and tools necessary to benefit from the project's outcomes, such as improved practices, products, and services.	Collect feedback from end-users on the practical impact of project outcomes.
Build Collaborative Networks	Strengthen partnerships and collaborations with other researchers, organizations, and industries by sharing valuable insights and contributing to knowledge exchange.	Monitor new partnerships formed, collaborative projects initiated, and joint publications.
Measure Impact	Evaluate the effectiveness of dissemination efforts in terms of audience engagement, understanding, and utilization of project outcomes.	Conduct surveys, interviews, and feedback analysis to assess the perceived impact of the dissemination activities.
Promote Sustainable Knowledge Sharing	Establish a foundation for continued knowledge sharing beyond the project's duration, ensuring the longevity of the project's impact.	Monitor ongoing engagement on communication channels and sustained interest in project outcomes.
Enhance Public Understanding	Enhance public understanding of the project's significance, contributing to a broader appreciation of scientific research and innovation.	Measure media coverage, public engagement events, and the reach of educational materials.

By accomplishing these objectives and goals, this dissemination plan aims to effectively communicate the project's value and contribute to its lasting impact on both the intended audience and society at large.

3. Target Audience

The first step is to identify the primary and secondary audiences for the dissemination efforts. To ensure that the communication efforts effectively reach the right people, this first crucial step starts with the investigation of the environment for user groups and organizations that can benefit from RADIOBLOCKS results.

The information gathering will be a two-step process:

1. Brainstorming with small groups
A stakeholder map will be created to identify individuals, organizations, and groups that have an interest in RADIOBLOCKS.
2. Questionnaires for all identified stakeholders
 - a. short term: targeted (email)
 - b. long term: open invitation (website, social media)

The information gathering will start with brainstorming sessions with a small group of project participants by selecting participants who have extensive networks inside and outside the project. Instead of a single large brainstorming session, the plan provides for several small ones involving groups that focus on several targeted subjects. The result of the brainstorming sessions will be a stakeholder map that categorizes the stakeholders based on their level of influence and involvement.

Based on the results of the brainstorming sessions, a questionnaire for all project stakeholders will be created. A targeted questionnaire will aim for quick reactions (via email). The list of recipients of the questionnaire is determined by the brainstorming sessions. This includes selected end-users (radio astronomers and engineers), experts in the field of antenna instrumentation, data scientists, and industry contacts.

Through the brainstorming sessions and the questionnaires, it will be possible to get a complete picture of the information needed. As the project progresses, more insights are gained: new stakeholders might emerge, or certain groups might be more interested than initially anticipated. Therefore, the plan will be adapted to address new target audiences. Tailoring the dissemination plan to address the right audiences will maximize the impact of RADIOBLOCKS's outcomes.

4. Dissemination Channels

Scientific discoveries

Goal: Share findings extensively within the scientific community and the public.

The dissemination of scientific discoveries resulting from the project actions will involve a multi-faceted approach to ensure that the findings reach a wide audience within the scientific community as well as the general public. This plan will focus on leveraging a variety of communication tools to maximize the visibility and impact of the project's results. The dissemination to the broader scientific community will be done in the normal way by the researchers with the support of their host institutes.

Researchers will publish their results in reputable peer-reviewed journals with gold or green open access. This approach ensures the findings are accessible to the broader scientific community, promoting rigorous review and validation. Furthermore, participation in national and international conferences will provide a platform for researchers to present their findings and engage in discussions with fellow experts. This approach fosters direct interaction and exchange of ideas.

Tools:

Research journals, conference participation, press releases and media relations, email/newsletter services, project's website, and social media platforms.

Technical developments

Goal: Disseminate documentation, technical specifications, and science verification in the broader technical community.

The dissemination of RADIOBLOCKS's technical developments and science verification results involves a strategic approach to ensure the effective sharing of documentation and specifications.

Documentation and specifications are hosted on the project SharePoint as a centralized resource. More details on the software documentation can be found in the Data Management Plan (D1.3). The results will be published in technical proceedings and scientific journals for wider audience reach to enable practical application and further advancements in the field.

Tools:

Microsoft SharePoint, technical and scientific journals, collaborative tools, and the project's website.

Software and simulated data products

Goal: Ensure the widespread availability, accessibility, and usability of the software and simulated data products.

The project will generate software and simulated data products that will be available under an open license. The dissemination will be achieved by utilizing open access to code and data, proper documentation, and suitable online platforms to publish and share the resources with the broader scientific community and interested parties.

Tools:

Project's website, GitHub, Zenodo (see D1.3), online discussion groups, conference participation, scientific and technical journals, email/newsletter services, press releases and media relations.

Technical design plans

Goals: Transparent communication, engagement, and sustained software use beyond funding.

Technical design plans will be stored and made publicly available except if special IP rights apply to them, in case the results are suitable for industrial or commercial exploitation. Detailed information on the research data management actions is described in the data management plan (D1.3). Sharing technical design plans with researchers, industrial partners, and the community will occur using key channels and tools such as the project website for resources and updates, publishing in research journals and conferences, using social media for updates and engagement, organizing workshops for training, newsletters, collaborating on platforms like Microsoft Teams, and issuing press releases for major milestones.

Tools:

Project's Website, scientific and technical journals, social media platforms, press releases and media relations, workshops, training courses, email/newsletter services, Microsoft SharePoint and other collaboration platforms.

Industrial collaborations

Goal: Enhance collaboration with industry partners for state-of-the-art equipment and techniques in radio astronomy.

Communication with industry, through the projects' Industry Advisory Board, will serve to optimize the synergy necessary to develop state-of-the-art equipment and techniques and to enhance the future fabrication phase of the developed instruments and methods. The

industry experts relevant to the radio astronomy communities will be invited to the project meetings and other technical events.

Tools:

Project Website, social media and media relations, email/newsletter services, RADIOBLOCKS's Industry Advisory Board meetings, workshops, conferences participation, press releases, Microsoft SharePoint and other collaborative platforms, and scientific and technical journals.

General public interest

Goal: Engage the general public in the excitement and impact of radio astronomy.

There is an enormous public interest in astronomy, and the partner institutes in the Consortium are some of the leading exponents of communicating the excitement and impact of astronomy in general and radio astronomy in particular with the general public. The project coordinator office in WP1 will support these local initiatives and work to maximize impact at the European level.

Tools:

Workshops, participation in educational outreach events, public talks and lectures, social media and media relations, project's website, and press releases.

Events

The events RADIOBLOCKS's members visit or organize for the dissemination of project products and results will be advertised on the RADIOBLOCKS website (www.radioblocks.eu). There will also be a page where organisations can propose to host events or request colocation of events. Every partner is requested to contribute to the dissemination and presentations will be published on the RADIOBLOCKS website as well. These presentations can include slide shows, posters, and movies.

General tools:

Print Media: Brochures, flyers, posters, and newspaper articles.

Online Media: Project website, social media platforms and online forums.

Events: Workshops, seminars, conferences, webinars, and public lectures.

Collaborative Platforms: Research networks, online communities, software repositories, and knowledge-sharing platforms.

5. Content Creation

To craft effective promotional materials, one must undertake a structured approach encompassing several key facets. Initially, there is a need to outline suitable content, ensuring its alignment with the intended message. The identification of the target audience should be both specific and comprehensive, allowing for tailored content delivery. Equally important is the selection of appropriate media channels to maximize reach and impact. This process of identification and information gathering is facilitated through the stakeholder mapping process. The promotional material needs to be built on a solid basis under consultation and feedback from the RADIOBLOCKS partners and the coordination of the project's communication officer.

Concerning the production phase, the content is gathered from experts within the project as the basis for the strategic design of the promotional materials to be distributed to the intended audience through various channels. This is, however, an iterative process, where feedback collection is crucial to generate insights for enhancement. Depending on the nature of the materials, they can be designed and built internally or outsourced to an outreach company.

6. Timeline

The timeline begins in September 2023, after the deadline for the Dissemination Plan as a project's deliverable. However, the relevant actions already started at the beginning of the project.

Timeline for information gathering:

Deadline	Activity
Sep 2023	Brainstorming with small groups
Nov 2023	Questionnaire design
Dec 2023	Distribute questionnaire
Jan 2024	Analyse the results of the questionnaire
Jan 2024	Internally publish stakeholders map and results of information gathering

Timeline for creation of promotional materials:

Deadline	Activity
Sep 2023	Solicit input to identify major conferences and corporate events
Dec 2023	Update the calendar of events
Dec 2023	Collect material for promotional material

Feb 2024	Create promotional material
Feb 2024	Update and distribute presentations, templates and demos
Apr-Sep 2024	Collect feedback
Oct 2024	Iterate and improve promotional material

Longer term timeline:

Period or deadline	Activity
2025	Repeat all steps, identify and act on higher ambitions
2026	Repeat all steps, identify and act on higher ambitions

7. Management

WP1 has hired a project communication officer, who will assist the coordinator and the management with the realization of the dissemination plan. The communication officer joined the project in September 2023. Their duties consist of continuously scanning the scientific and industrial landscape surrounding the RADIOBLOCKS consortium in search of short- and long-term dissemination opportunities. They will be in contact with the RADIOBLOCKS partners and WP leaders to activate them in identifying and guaranteeing follow-up on these opportunities.

WP1, supported by the project's communication officer, will monitor and coordinate the successful implementation of the dissemination plan.

The project management sets boundary conditions to keep the focus. With new information, these boundary conditions can be moved in a managed way. For this purpose, deadlines are included both to meet the goals on time and also to limit the time spent on every step, as a metric to keep the boundary conditions within limits.

It is important to use the knowledge within the various partners about connections and contacts and create new ones in every step of the plan. Maintaining a lesson-learned register will facilitate spreading good practice.

Risks should be monitored throughout the project. The initially identified risks are listed in Section 9.

It is worth noticing that a successful dissemination plan is adaptable and responsive to changing circumstances. WP1 will regularly review and update the plan to ensure it remains effective in reaching the intended audiences and achieving the project's goals.

8. Budget/Resources

The resources needed for this task are not budgeted for explicitly in the project plan. The dissemination plan will be managed from WP1 under the supervision of the project coordinator. The Project Communication Officer, with an effort of 0.8 FTE, will be dedicated to the execution of the plan.

The work for the dissemination plan, such as information gathering, feedback, promotion at events, publications and press releases, will be spread over all WPs and all partners to minimize the effort and maximize the impact.

9. Risk Management

The risks identified within the definition of this plan are:

Risk	Mitigation plan
No useful results in the brainstorming sessions	Use a tight agenda for the brainstorming sessions and invite committed persons
Too many results from the brainstorming sessions, resulting in unfocused follow-up	End the brainstorming session with a selection round to create a priority list
No useful results on the first questionnaires	Create short clear questions that lead to short clear answers that can be completed with minimal effort
Too many results from the questionnaires, resulting in unfocused follow-up	Create focused questions, so the results should not be too diverse. Create a priority list and template that the answers should fit in
People involved are not active enough, resulting in not enough progress.	The task leader should follow the process closely, setting many small targets with nearby deadlines. Create an easy reporting mechanism for easy follow-up
People involved are too active in certain areas, resulting in missing focus in follow-up areas.	The task leader should follow the process closely, setting many small targets with nearby deadlines. Create an easy reporting mechanism for easy follow-up
Promotional material does not cover all areas of RADIOBLOCKS.	Create a priority list that shows the areas that should be covered
Promotional material does not connect to the presenter, resulting in low-quality presentation and less potential for exploitation of products and results	Make sure presenters are ambassadors by requesting feedback on the promotional material before a presentation is given